

PLAY IS AN IMPORTANT TOOL FOR THE COMPREHENSIVE DEVELOPMENT OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract: The game determines the degree to which children's future educational and work activities, attitudes towards people are formed, the child's cognitive activity develops on the basis of game activities, the better the child plays in the preschool age, the better he learns at school. The article provides information on the fact that games are an important tool for all-round development of children, the importance of physical education and games in the formation of moral and moral qualities in children.

Key words: Game, preschool education, sport, physical qualities, physical education, training, children.

INTRODUCTION

Physical well-being is a guarantee of health, it helps to develop a person in all aspects and educate young people. The main task of the educational process is to strengthen the dynamism and stability of educational activities, to guarantee high educational results. This is based on the personality of the pedagogue, which takes into account the individual characteristics of the student. Health plays an important role in human life, especially in youth. The level of health is the reason for a person's professional maturity and creative growth. The pursuit of physical maturity is understood as a pedagogical process that ensures optimal adaptation of a person to various life conditions and improves his physical condition, physical and functional fitness, body structure and physical development, which is considered the source of his active creative life, educational and future work activities, his place in life.

As we know, psychologists consider play to be the leading activity during preschool age. In the game, all aspects of the child's personality are formed by interacting with each other. By watching a child playing, you can learn about his interests, perceptions of the environment, and his attitude towards adults and friends.

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The State Curriculum of Pre-school Education "Ilk Qadam" has shown the importance of organizing educational activities in development centers for effective preparation of children for school education.

The game plays an important role in the system of physical education of children, in the educational work of the preschool educational organization, moral, labor and aesthetic education.

In the game, the demands and needs of a young organism are satisfied, vital activity increases, unity, freshness, and cheerfulness are cultivated.

During the game, children acquire new knowledge, skills, and develop their abilities. Cooperative games help children get closer to each other, unite, and raise their spirits. It is games that help to gain children's trust and inclination towards the teacher. The game has long attracted the attention of famous scientists, pedagogues-psychologists, philosophers, sociologists, ethnographers and cultural figures.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

If we look at the history of Central Asian culture, a lot of attention is paid to raising children in the family. Among the famous scholars, Abu Nasr Farabi, Abu Rayhan Beruni, Abu Ali ibn Sina, Yusuf Hos Hajib, Ahmad Yugnakiy have reflected on the upbringing of children typical of our people in their works.

During the study of folk pedagogy, in the works of scientists on child education and manners, we see that the most effective method of educational work in raising children is the game form.

Pedagogical scientists P.F. Lesgaft, K.D. The game theory was developed by Ushinsky, the emergence of the game on the basis of the labor process and its role in preparing the young generation for work, the importance of the content of the game in the formation of the child's personality was explained by K.D. Ushinsky explained.

When researching the origins of art, Russian scholars pay attention to children's games. According to them, in the history of people, games, like art, appeared after the appearance of work and on its basis.

P.F. Lesgaft said, "The child imitates the events around him in his first game, the game reflects the social reality." The great psychologist D.V. Elkonin proposes a new idea about the origin of the game. In the early development of society, convenient toy tools were developed for children to participate in the life and work of adults, and for children to work. As a result of the appearance of toy-weapons, role-playing games appear. D.V. Elkonin put forward the idea of the need to awaken the desire to work in a child by participating in the work of adults.

Educational activity develops on the basis of the game process. The more a child plays at a young age, the better it will be at school and later on at work. L.S. Vygotsky distinguishes the following incredible aspects of the game:

1. The child follows the path of least resistance (provides satisfaction), but learns to act on the path of greatest resistance. The game is a school of will and skill.

2. Usually a child feels a sense of obedience even in giving up what he wants, and here obedience is the path to the greatest satisfaction. The game gives the child a new form of desire, that is, it compares the desire with its role in the game and its rules. In the game, the child can achieve the highest results, which

tomorrow will become his real average level, his morality.

L.S. Vygotsky describes the game as a means of mastering the inner social world of the child, social orders. In preschool pedagogy, game theory is considered a social activity and appears in the process of historical development of work. Children always reflect life in their games. Therefore, its content changes in social reality. A game is a goal-oriented process.

In the pedagogy of preschool education, the cultural hygiene skills that a child should acquire are divided into the following groups: a) eating skills (taking food in an orderly manner, chewing well, using a spoon, fork, napkin, etc.) b) taking care of one's own body care skills (washing, combing hair, etc.) v) keeping order in the room, using and caring for clothes (quick dressing and undressing, keeping things neat and orderly, etc.) physical exercises that acquire skills and competences are also determined: a) basic movements (walking, running, jumping, climbing, throwing, balance exercises): general developmental exercises, standing up and standing up again: b) sports exercises (swimming, skiing sledding, skating, etc.). Action games (with a plot, without a plot, games with sports components, etc.) are also shown, long walks outside the plot are planned in summer and winter. The main document defining the content of physical education work is "Kindergarten Education and Training Program". It allows children to learn skills and abilities of consistent movement, develops coordination of movements and develops finding a way in space, develops physical qualities (agility, speed, endurance). The growing organism of a preschool child needs full sleep and regular nutrition, because the energy spent on an activity is replaced by energy, as well as energy is needed to add energy related to the processes of growth and development. The nervous tissue of the child's brain cannot be in a state of activity for a long time. Strengthening of nervous processes, which is especially evident in young children, leads not only to rapid fatigue of directly moving tissues, but also to fatigue of the cerebral cortex. The

activity of the nervous tissues of the child's brain is much lower than that of adults. The shell of the child's brain is actively formed. A large number of conditioned reflex connections are formed, which requires additional nerve input. Children are very interested in such toys. In some independent games, children cannot immediately show activity and initiative, their movements are varied and limited.

But by fulfilling the tasks of adults, children's actions in fish games are directed to a specific goal, they repeat the actions several times, strengthen their movement skills and develop agility and dexterity. It is very important to guide children even when they are busy playing. Often, in independent games, children perform incorrect and even dangerous actions - they jump over a chair or a pole with almost straight legs, resting on the soles of their feet; they run pushing off the ground with the soles of their feet. In such cases, different ways are used: an adult enters the game himself; reminds children of a familiar and close image that they can imitate (how a cat gently jumps, how birds fly quietly). The first games that should be taught to children will not have a specific plot and rules. The child performs simple, interesting tasks: he comes, takes the toy, runs to the adults and sees what is hidden in their hands. ("Take the flag", "Run to me", "Find the flag"). A certain consistency should be observed when teaching games. For example, catch me is easier than catch you. In the first case, the child must catch an older person; in the second game there is a risk of being caught, so the child has to spend more physical effort. It is necessary that the games become richer and more varied in content, and include more complex tasks. If the child initially runs at the pace he wants to get the toy, after the game is well mastered, the pace of running should be determined by an adult. At the same time, in plot-role games, the child's experience of the game and, especially, of real (true) interactions forms the basis of a special feature of thinking, thanks to which he learns the point of view of other people, predicts their further actions. there is an opportunity to know and

shape their behavior accordingly.

The role-playing game is of decisive importance in the development of imagination. In game activities, the child learns to replace the same objects with others, to assume different roles. All this helps to develop the imagination. Substitute objects and many other play activities are not necessary in the games of older preschool children. Children begin to create new situations in their imagination by comparing objects and activities with them. The game can be played internally.

CONCLUSION

The impact of the game on the development of the child's personality is that through it, the child gets to know how adults walk, stand, and interact, which serve as a model for his own behavior; in the game, the child learns the basic skills of communication, qualities necessary for establishing relationships with peers. The game, which completely covers the child, forces him to obey the rules according to his role, helps the development of feelings and improves the ability to control behavior through will. As part of the game activity, educational activity also begins to form, and later it takes the leading place. Educational elements are introduced by an adult, they do not directly come from the essence of the game.

A preschooler learns while playing - he looks at reading as a kind of role-playing game with certain rules. However, on the basis of following these rules, the child learns the simplest learning activities without realizing it. A child of preschool age develops a desire to study and begins to form initial knowledge. Preschool children spend most of their time playing. The game is an important means of all-round development of children of preschool age, it is their main activity. During the game, the personality of the child begins to form as a subject of activity.

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